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Correction: Preparation and property investigation of chain end functionalized *cis*-1,4 polybutadienes via de-polymerization and cross metathesis of *cis*-1,4 polybutadienes

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Correction for 'Preparation and property investigation of chain end functionalized *cis*-1,4 polybutadienes via de-polymerization and cross metathesis of *cis*-1,4 polybutadienes' by Weilun Ying *et al.*, *Polym. Chem.*, 2019, **10**, 3525–3534.

The authors acknowledge that the same procedure for the preparation of telechelic polyolefins by the cross-metathesis functionalization from *cis*-1,4-polybutadiene adopted in this manuscript was previously reported in ref. 21f [X. L. Michel, S. Fouquay, G. Michaud, F. Simon, J.-M. Brusson, J.-F. Carpentier and S. M. Guillaume, *Eur. Polym. J.*, 2017, **96**, 403–413].

The Royal Society of Chemistry apologises for these errors and any consequent inconvenience to authors and readers.

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